

To Investigate the Relationship Between Cord Blood Albumin and Serum Bilirubin Levels in Term Healthy Babies At 48 Hours

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Abstract

Aim: To study the correlation between various levels of cord blood albumin & serum bilirubin at 48 hrs of age in term healthy newborns. **Methods:** A prospective study was conducted in the Department of Paediatrics, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar India for 1 year. 100 terms healthy newborns with birth weight ≥ 2.5 kg was included in this study. Newborns with a congenital anomaly, birth asphyxia, traumatic birth, respiratory distress, sepsis, metabolic diseases, pathological hyperbilirubinemia before 24 hrs, infant of a diabetic mother, and haemolytic diseases requiring admission in NICU were excluded from the study. Cord blood was collected at birth and analysed by auto analyser method for Cord Serum Albumin level. Newborns were divided into 3 groups for data analysis according to their cord albumin levels (<2.8 , $2.8-3.4$, and >3.4 g/dl), and were analysed to find out association with 3 risk zone according to Bhutani nomogram. **Results:** Out of the 100 infants enrolled in our study, 60(60%) were males and 40(40%). 20% newborn had cord albumin <2.8 g/dl, 50% recorded values between 2.8 to 3.4 g/dl and 30(30%) recorded cord albumin >3.4 g/dl. Newborns with higher birth weight had a significantly lesser incidence of low cord albumin (<2.8 g/dl). Out of 100 newborns, 20(20%) serum bilirubin levels were at the low-risk zone, 57(57%) at the low intermediate risk zone, while 23 (23%) were at the high intermediate risk zone at 48 hrs of age. 60% of newborns with cord albumin level <2.8 g/dl recorded serum bilirubin at or above high intermediate risk zone, while 7 were at low intermediate risk zone and 1 new-born was at low-risk zone at 48 hrs of age. We found that a cut-off level of cord blood albumin of 2.8 g/dl had 84.9% sensitivity, 82.7% specificity, and PPV 85.1% for prediction of hyperbilirubinemia at high intermediate cut-off level with a p-value of <0.05 in term newborns, with NPV of 76% indicating its usefulness. **Conclusion:** Neonates with cord blood albumin <2.8 gm/dl had a significant association of the development of hyperbilirubinemia at or above intermediate high-risk zone according to Bhutani nomogram at 48 hrs of life.

Keywords: Neonates, Cord Blood, Albumin, Bilirubin.

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Introduction

Jaundice in newborn is a very common problem. Neonatal Hyperbilirubinemia (NH) may lead to kernicterus in otherwise healthy newborns. This can be easily prevented if excessive hyperbilirubinemia for age is promptly identified and appropriately treated[1-3]. Newborns can be screened for severity of bilirubinemia before hospital discharge which may help in early detection of the newborns at risk for excessive hyperbilirubinemia during the first week of life[4]. It is difficult to predict which of these newborns are at risk for developing significant hyperbilirubinemia (Total Serum Bilirubin \geq 15mg/dl)[5]. Significant hyperbilirubinemia is usually found in 3% of normal term babies[6]. Depending on various methods of bilirubin estimation in different laboratories, the frequency of breast feeding, ethnic makeup of people and regional variations the incidence of hyperbilirubinemia changes[7-9]. The severe jaundice and kernicterus has been found in some healthy full term newborns discharged early with no apparent hemolysis[10].

The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) recommends that newborns discharged within 48 hours should have a follow-up visit after 2-3 days to detect significant jaundice and other problems[11]. In developing countries like India, this recommendation is not practical due to limited follow up facilities.

Early treatment of jaundice with phototherapy is effective, simple and cheap as compared to the treatment of severe neonatal jaundice with exchange transfusion, which is time consuming, costly, associated with complications and requires skilled personnel. Thus, the early prediction of jaundice offers an attractive option for picking up babies at risk of NH. Many investigators have tried to find a simple marker to predict hyperbilirubinemia and its subsequent course in newborns like cord bilirubin estimation, bilirubin estimation during 6 to

24 hours of age, predischage hour specific bilirubin estimation and transcutaneous bilirubin measurement[12,13].

Materials and methods:

A prospective study was conducted in the Department of Paediatrics, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar India for 1 year, after taking the approval of the protocol review committee and institutional ethics committee. 100 terms healthy newborns with birth weight \geq 2.5 kg were included in this study. Newborns with a congenital anomaly, birth asphyxia, traumatic birth, respiratory distress, sepsis, metabolic diseases, pathological hyperbilirubinemia before 24 hrs, infant of a diabetic mother, and haemolytic diseases requiring admission in NICU were excluded from the study.

Methodology:

Cord blood was collected at birth and analysed by auto analyser method for Cord Serum Albumin level. Venous blood samples were collected from the baby at 48 hours of life. Serum bilirubin estimation is done within 12 hours of collection of a sample by Diazotized sulfanilic test. Gestational age was assessed using Ballard score, SGA, AGA and LGA were defined using Fenton chart. Newborns were divided into 3 groups for data analysis according to their cord albumin levels (<2.8, 2.8-3.4, and >3.4 g/dl), and were analysed to find out association with 3 risk zone according to Bhutani nomogram. Bilirubin level at or above high intermediate risk zone (over 75th percentile cutoff value 11.3mg/dl) at 48 hrs of age was considered a cutoff value to find out the association with cord blood albumin level[14,15].

Statistical Analysis:

Data was entered on the computer using Microsoft Office Excel Software program for Windows, and then transferred to the Statistical Package of Social Science Software (SPSS) 21.0. Comparison

between groups was performed using the Mann-Whitney test for quantitative variables while comparison for qualitative variables was performed through Chi-square or Fisher's test. P values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results:

Out of the 100 infants enrolled in our study, 60(60%) were males and 40(40%). 20% newborn had cord albumin <2.8 g/dl, 50% recorded values between 2.8 to 3.4 g/dl and 30(30%) recorded cord albumin >3.4 g/dl. Newborns with higher birth weight had a significantly lesser incidence of low cord albumin (<2.8). gestational age and gender of the study population did not have a significant association with low cord albumin. (Table 1)

Out of 100 newborns, 20(20%) serum bilirubin levels were at the low-risk zone, 57(57%) at the low intermediate risk zone, while 23 (23%) were at the high intermediate risk zone at 48 hrs of age. 60% of newborns with cord albumin level <2.8 g/dl recorded serum bilirubin at or above high intermediate risk zone, while 7 were at low intermediate risk zone and 1 new-born were at low-risk zone at 48 hrs of age. This correlation was statistically significant. [$\chi^2= 118.78$; Likelihood Ratio=113.11; $P=<0.05^*$] (table 2) We found that a cut-off level of cord blood albumin of 2.8g/dl had 84.9% sensitivity, 82.7% specificity, and PPV 85.1% for prediction of hyperbilirubinemia at high intermediate cut-off level with a p-value of <0.05 in term newborns, with NPV of 76% indicating its usefulness.

Table 1: Demographic profile of study population according to cord blood albumin at birth

		Cord blood albumin(g/dl)			total	
		<2.8	2.8-3.4	>3.4		
Gender	Male	13	30	17	60(60%)	>0.05
	Female	7	20	13	40(40%)	
Birth Weight	2.5-3	10	17	3	30 (30%)	<0.05*
	3.1-3.5	5	30	7	42(42%)	
	>3.5	5	3	20	28 (28%)	
Gestational age	mean age	36.5	37.2	37.3	77(77%)	>0.05
	37-40 wk	13	45	19		
	>40 wk	7	5	11	23(23%)	

Table 2: Comparison of Cord blood albumin at birth and Total serum bilirubin at 48 hrs of age

Cord blood albumin(g/dl)	serum bilirubin at 48 hrs of age (mg/dl)				p-value
	Low-risk zone	Low intermediate-risk zone	High intermediate-risk zone	total	
<2.8	1(5%)	7 (35%)	12 (60%)	20	p <0.05*
2.8-3.4	1 (2%)	41 (82%)	8 (16%)	50	
>3.4	18 (60%)	9 (30%)	3 (10%)	30	
Total	20 (20%)	57(57%)	23 (23%)	100	

[P=<0.05*]

Discussion:

According to recent AAP guidelines, healthy term newborns should be discharged within 48 hours of birth[16].

Hence it is necessary to identify the newborns at risk of developing hyperbilirubinemia following an early discharge from the hospital to avoid

readmissions and complications as bilirubin encephalopathy and long-term complications[17]. Albumin has a role in the transport and clearance of bilirubin. Albumin acts as a carrier protein for the transport of bilirubin, which eventually helps in the transfer of bilirubin to the liver where conjugation occurs.

Bilirubin binds to albumin in an equimolar ratio. Around 8.5 mg of bilirubin will bind covalently to 1 g of albumin, this process is interrupted due to decreased albumin levels in newborns. It is documented in the literature that newborns have an immature liver function as compared to adults leading to decreased production and synthesis of all the major proteins including albumin which has a major role in the conjugation of bilirubin.

And the neonatal liver is also immature with less ability to excrete and handle excessive production of bilirubin than can be caused by various aetiologies in newborns. Low production of albumin in newborns will lower its transport and binding capacity and may increase bilirubin in these newborns[18]. In the present study we aimed to assess the correlation between cord blood albumin and serum bilirubin for early identification of hyperbilirubinemia and use of cord blood Albumin level as a tool for screening for the risk of subsequent Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia.

There are a few studies that predict Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia by estimating cord blood bilirubin levels but vary in opinion. In our study we found that a cut-off level of cord blood albumin of 2.8g/dl had 84.9% sensitivity, 82.7% specificity, and PPV 85.1% for prediction of hyperbilirubinemia for high intermediate cut-off level with a p-value of <0.05 in term newborns, with NPV of 76% indicating its usefulness. Reshad M, Ravichander B et al.[19] with the sample size of 175 terms and preterm newborn found that cord blood albumin level ≤ 2.8 g/dL is a sensitive limit, with good sensitivity and positive predictive value, in both term and preterm

neonates and Cord blood albumin level ≥ 3.4 g/dL was found to be relatively safe for neonates.

Similar observations were made by Gaurav Aiyappa et al.[20] [71.8%] with 71.8% sensitivity and 65.1% with a sample size of 165 newborns. In the present study, there is a statistically significant correlation between birth weight and cord blood albumin and between birth weight and serum bilirubin in term neonates with good sensitivity and specificity. As we did not take preterm neonates making our results more specific to term newborns. Sahu et al.[21] the study of 40 neonates also showed that 70% of newborns who developed significant neonatal hyperbilirubinemia had cord serum albumin level < 2.8 g/dl, 30% newborns had cord albumin level 2.9- 3.3 g/dl and none of the newborns with cord albumin >3.4g/dl developed neonatal hyperbilirubinemia, and 80% neonates with cord albumin less than 2.8 mg/dl required phototherapy.

Statistical significance was noted between cord albumin with development of significant hyperbilirubinemia (p-value <0.001). In a study by Trivedi et al.[22] 205 newborns out of 605 developed neonatal hyperbilirubinemia with 58.35% (120/205) of the neonates with cord albumin level <2.8 g/dl developing significant neonatal hyperbilirubinemia required intervention with statistical significance of P <0.05. A study by Meena KJ et al.[23] found that cord bilirubin level >2.5 mg/dl had a sensitivity of 77%, specificity of 98.6% with NPV of 96% which supports the results of the present study. Pahuja et al.[24] also observed that the predictive value of cord albumin to detect neonatal hyperbilirubinemia was 75% with 61.3% sensitivity, and 76.8% specificity following the Present study. Similar observations were also made by Asit Kumar et al.[25] Dr Pushpanjali et al.[26] Dhanjal SS et al.[27] and Pathak NN et al.[28].

Conclusion:

Neonates with cord blood albumin <2.8 gm/dl had a significant association of the development of hyperbilirubinemia at or above intermediate high-risk zone according to Bhutani nomogram at 48 hrs of life.

Reference:

1. Piazza AJ, Stoll BJ. Jaundice and Hyperbilirubinemia in the Newborn. In: Kliegman RM, Behrman RE, Jenson HB, Stanton BF, editors. Nelson textbook of Pediatrics: 19 th Ed. New Delhi; Saunders Elsevier, 2012; 1:603–12
2. Penn AA, Enzmann DR, Hahn JS. Kernicterus in full term infant. Pediatrics. 1994 Jun 6; 93:1003–6.
3. Stevenson DK. Kernicterus in a full-term infant: the need for increased vigilance. Pediatrics. 1995; 95:799.
4. Newman TB, Maisles MJ. Does hyperbilirubinemia damage the brain of healthy full-term infants? ClinPerinatol. 1990; 17:331–1335.
5. Maisles MJ, Newman TB. Kernicterus in Otherwise Healthy Breast-fed Term Newborns. Pediatrics. 1995 Oct; 96:730– 33.
6. Martin CR, Cloherty JP. Neonatal Hyperbilirubinemia. In: Cloherty JP, Eichenwald EC, Stark AR, editors. Manual of neonatal care: 6th Ed. New Delhi: Wolters Kluwer, 2008; 304–39.
7. Bahl L, Sharma R, Sharma J. Etiology of Neonatal Jaundice in Shimla. Indian Pediatr. 1994 Oct; 31:1275–78.
8. Murki S, Majumudhar S, Marwaha N. Risk factors of Kernicterus in term babies with Non haemolytic Jaundice. Indian Pediatr. 2001 Jul; 38(7):757–62.
9. Moyer VA, Ahn C, Sneed S. Accuracy of clinical judgment in neonatal jaundice. Arch PediatrAdolesc Med. 2000; 154:391–4.
10. Seidman DS, Stevenson DK, Ergaz Z. Hospital readmission due to neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. Pediatrics. 1996; 96:727–9.
11. American Academy of Pediatrics Clinical Practice Guideline and Subcommittee on Hyperbilirubinemia. Management of hyperbilirubinemia in the newborn Infant 35 or more weeks of Gestation. Pediatrics. 2004 Jul 1; 114:297–316.
12. Bernaldo AJN. Bilirubin dosage in cord blood: could it predict neonatal hyperbilirubinemia? Sao Paulo Med J. 2004 May 6; 122(3):99–103.
13. Knupfer M, Pulzer F, Gebauer C, Robel-Tillig E, Vogtmann C. Predictive value of umbilical cord blood bilirubin for postnatal hyperbilirubinaemia. ActaPaediatr. 2005 May; 94(5):581–7.
14. SiyahBilgin B, Altun Koroglu O, Yalaz M, Karaman S, Kultursay N. Factors affecting bilirubin levels during first 48 hours of life in healthy infants. Biomed Res Int. 2013;316430.
15. Bhutani VK, Johnson L, Sivieri EM. Predictive ability of a pre-discharge hour-specific serum bilirubin for subsequent significant hyperbilirubinemia in healthy term and near-term newborns. Pediatrics. 1999 Jan;103(1)6-14.
16. American Academy of Pediatrics Subcommittee on Hyperbilirubinemia. Management of hyperbilirubinemia in the newborn infant 35 or more weeks of gestation. Pediatrics. 2004 Jul;114(1)297- 316.
17. Zimmerman DR, Klinger G, Merlob P. Early discharge after delivery- A study of safety and risk factors. Scientific World Journal. 2003 Dec 18;3:1363-9.
18. Rosenthal P. Assessing liver function and hyperbilirubinemia in the newborn, National Academy of Clinical Biochemistry. Clin Chem. 1997 Jan;43(1)228-34.
19. Reshad M, B Ravichander, T S Raghuraman. A study of cord blood albumin as a predictor of significant neonatal hyperbilirubinemia in term and preterm neonates. Int J Res Med Sci. 2016;4(3)887-90.
20. Aiyappa GKC, Shriyan A, Raj B. Cord blood albumin as a predictor of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia in healthy neonates. Int J ContempPediatr. 2017;4;503e6.

21. Sahu, Suchanda, et al. "Cord blood albumin as a predictor of neonatal jaundice". *Int J Biol Med Res.* 2011;2(1)436-438.
22. Trivedi D J, et al. "Umbilical cord blood bilirubin level measurement in predicting the development of significant hyperbilirubinemia". *J Int Sci Inn Tech Sec.* 2013(2)39-42.
23. Meena K J, Singh S, Verma R C, Sharma R. Utility of cord blood albumin as a predictor of significant neonatal jaundice in healthy term newborns. *PedOncall.* 2015;12(4)112-16.
24. Pahuja, Mayank, Shikha Dhawan, Sanjata Roy Chaudhary. "Correlation of cord blood bilirubin and neonatal hyperbilirubinemia in healthy newborns. " *Int J ContempPediatr.* 2016;3(926)e30.
25. Mishra AK, Sanyasi Naidu C. Association of cord serum albumin with neonatal hyperbilirubinemia among term appropriate-for-gestational-age neonates. *Int J PediatrAdolesc Med.* 2018 Dec;5(4)142-144
26. Pushpanjali, Anil kumar Chaudhary. To study utility of cord albumin as predictor of significant neonatal jaundice in tertiary care hospital of Jharkhand. *Indian journal of applied research.* 2018;8(3).
27. Dhanjal GS, Rathi RK, Agrawal S, Savita. Cord serum albumin as a predictor of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia in healthy full-term neonates. *Int J Pediatr Res.* 2018;5(4)203-208.
28. Pathak NN, Deka A, Arvind P. Cord blood albumin, a tool as predictor of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia requiring intervention. *The New Indian Journal of OBGYN.* 2020;7(1)93-6.